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“Frankie the Frog”: The Total Transformation of a River Basin as “Totalitarian” Technology (Spain, 1946-1961).

Abstract: After the Spanish Civil War (1936-1939), Francisco Franco’s emphasis on dam building became so intense that it is still today associated with his dictatorial rule. Rather than being purely a personal obsession, however, this intensive period of reservoir construction was the result of the influential political role played by engineers from the early years of the regime. During the years 1946 to 1961 some of these engineers undertook the “total transformation” of the Noguera Ribagorzana river basin in the Catalanian Pyrenees. But this explicitly “totalitarian” project encountered important limitations posed both by competing state agencies and by the basin’s geology. Analysing the efforts of these engineers allows for new understandings of the Francoist regime and of the place of science, technology, and the landscape within it.

Frankie the Frog and the Role of Engineers

On the morning of 17 June 1953, General Francisco Franco Bahamonde (1892-1975), “*Caudillo* of Spain by God’s grace”, watched Ramón Iglésias i Navarri, Bishop of Urgell, as he offered his blessings to the mechanisms of the hydropower station of Llesp, at the Noguera Ribagorzana river. They were surrounded by a group of engineers, some of them with ministerial duties, well satisfied with the authorities’ public acknowledgment of their success. This image of Franco inaugurating reservoirs is commonly associated with the nearly forty years of his dictatorial rule installed after the Spanish Civil War (1936-1939). Between 1940 and 1967, some 300 reservoirs were built in Spain both for agricultural and industrial usages, thereby changing the appearance and economy of the country. Jumping from the opening of one reservoir to the next, *el Caudillo* was soon mockingly baptized as *Paco el Rana* –Frankie the Frog.¹

The proliferation of reservoirs during Francoism speaks of how scientists and engineers contributed to shaping the regime from its earliest stages. Science in authoritarian regimes has commonly been interpreted as inherently biased towards the

¹ The translation “Paco el rana” for “Frankie the frog” comes from Erik Swyngedouw, “Technonatural Revolutions: the Scalar Politics of Franco’s Hydro-social Dream for Spain, 1939–1975”, *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 32 (2007), 9–28, on 10 and 20-21.

search for political legitimacy or towards the absolute ruler's personal obsessions. This historiographical approach depicts experts –whether scientists or engineers– as working *under* the designs of their ruler or his party, rather than as active participants within the regime.² Repression, censorship and political mandates and ideologies surely had an effect on Francoist science and technology.³ This paper, however, focuses on gauging scientists and engineers' active role in producing those political mandates and ideologies. Their technical projects were intertwined with the country's political economy.

Particularly illuminating is the “total transformation” of the Noguera Ribagorzana River in the region of the Aragonian and Catalan Pyrenees. In the fifteen short years between 1946 and 1961, a state company installed 12 power stations there. The engineers promoting the project insisted that the “systematization” of this basin entailed its “total control”. This meant both scientifically controlling the geological and hydrological characteristics of the basin as well as seizing political and legal power over the Noguera's waters. As a venture in achieving total control, taming the Noguera's waters would become an exemplary model for the “totalitarian” control of the political economy which some of these engineers strongly favoured. By this, they meant controlling *all* aspects of an issue from a *single* command centre.⁴ In the course of this pursuit, however, both interrelated and mutually dependent aspects of total control –the technical and the political– met with considerable hindrances. Exploring this episode shows how scientists and engineers assumed a central role in shaping Francoist Spain and providing it with material content.

Noguera Ribagorzana: the Total Transformation of a River Basin

Winding 130 km from its main source to its mouth at the Segre River, the Noguera Ribagorzana eventually joins its waters with those of the Ebro River, which lends its name to “Iberia”. From its 2,500 m heights to its union with the Segre at 150 m, the waters of its 2.030 km² basin traverse a steep landscape of gorges, peaks, and

² Susanne Heim, Carola Sachse and Mark Walker (eds.), *The Kaiser Wilhelm Society under National Socialism* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009).

³ Santiago López, “Franco's Dams as Evidence of Technological Regression” *History and Technology*, 30 (2010): 228 and following.

⁴ Jean-Pierre Faye, *Théorie du récit: introduction aux langages totalitaires* (Paris: Hermann Editeurs des Sciences et des Arts, 1972): part 2, chapter 1. Robert O. Paxton, “Comparisons and Definitions” in R. J. B. Bosworth (ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Fascism* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009): 547-565.

valleys. High rainfall and melting snow increase flow in spring and summer. The Noguera's potential for hydraulic power production had been recognised by a number of private electric companies, most of which had undertaken hydraulic works in the area's other basins, which fed the many industries in Barcelona with electricity. In the 1920s and 1930s these companies obtained water rights to generate electricity at various stretches of the Noguera; by the early 1940s they had developed plans for a number of hydropower stations.⁵

After the Civil War, however, the political situation changed dramatically. In 1940, Army engineer Antonio Suanzes (1891-1977), minister of Industry and Commerce under Franco from 1938 to 1939 and again from 1944 to 1951, pushed for the creation of the National Institute for Industry (INI). This holding of state companies drew from both the Italian Istituto per la Ricostruzione Industriale and the Spanish military tradition of economic protectionism. Suanzes conceived of it as a tool for industrialization and import substitution.⁶ While Suanzes conceded that the bulk of the economy had to be entrusted to private firms, he held that the state should guarantee the good health of those industrial branches considered "of national interest". In some cases, this ultimately meant the nationalization of an entire production sector. Suanzes argued that for INI's companies to be efficient and strong, they needed to function independently of the private economy; they needed, in other words, to produce their own energy. Suanzes expected INI's industries to develop so strongly that they would represent 5% of the total Spanish electricity consumption. Production aspirations, he reasoned, should aim at such a mark.

The Noguera Ribagorzana River soon attracted Suanzes's attention. If it could be transformed into an energy production plant and connected to the INI's Escatrón thermal power station, it could fuel the INI's industrial plans in Catalonia and further south.⁷ In 1931, engineer Victoriano Muñoz Oms (1900-2000) had founded a private company to extract coal at the Noguera basin with a group of what he considered "the

⁵ See the various plans in AGA, Alcalá de Henares, (04)53, Box 25/17343.

⁶ Pablo Martín Aceña and Francisco Comín, *INI: 50 años de industrialización en España*, (Madrid: Espasa-Calpe, 1991). Elena San Román, *Ejército e industria: el nacimiento del INI* (Barcelona: Crítica, 1999).

⁷ INI, "Bosquejo de plan de aprovechamiento integral del río Noguera Ribagorzana y sus afluentes", SEPI, Madrid, Box 1202 (Estudios, informes y proyectos técnicos 1943-1946), Folder 15, E. 3393 (23 June 1944): 3.

romantic pioneers who discovered the industrial world of the Leridan Pyrenees.”⁸ In 1935 the Catalanian government commissioned him to prepare an official plan for hydropower in the region. The plan contemplated collaborating with three private companies who had projects for damming the Noguera. After the Civil War, however, Muñoz approached Suanzes as a stronger collaborator. Around 1942, Suanzes initiated a series of negotiations with the private companies enjoying legal rights to the Noguera’s hydraulic use.⁹ For him, economic independence, or autarky, for both the INI and the Spanish political economy as a whole, required the “totalitarian action of the state over the economy”.¹⁰

For Suanzes, total transformation of the Noguera Ribagorzana was an essential step in this “totalitarian” action. He argued that total control of the basin was indispensable for the river’s optimal electrical output. “Integral regulation” of the river would lead it to produce 20% of the Spanish total consumption.¹¹ The argument was technical, but its implications were immediately political: coordinating different stretches of the river would be a real possibility only if the project for the river’s transformation was drawn by a single hand and put in practice by a company big enough to direct all the works necessary. Moreover, this company should not be private, since only the state could understand that production, and not profits, was the goal of the river’s transformation. Only the state had the resources and long-term perspective that the task demanded. Suanzes was able to convince Franco and his closest collaborators of the importance of the Noguera to the INI’s autarkic plans and, in 1946, the INI founded ENHER (Noguera Ribagorzana Hydro-electric National Company) with the charge to work the river. Eduardo Torroja, a renowned structural engineer, was appointed president. Muñoz was named executive director.

ENHER engineers saw the Noguera’s total transformation as a unique project. They stressed the gendered idea of a “virgin” river to be conquered, depicting the region as emptied and abandoned by cattle-herders in search of more promising city jobs. They

⁸ Victoriano Muñoz Oms, “Conferencia sobre ENHER”, (Dec. 4, 1961).

⁹ On the INI’s long litigations with private companies regarding the Noguera Ribagorzana, see Antonio Gómez Mendoza, *Electra y el Estado. La intervención pública en la industria eléctrica bajo el franquismo, Vol. II*, (Pamplona: Comisión Nacional de la Energía, 2007): 139–182, 334–344 and 368–371.

¹⁰ Antonio Gómez-Mendoza and Elena San-Román, “Competition between Private and Public Enterprise in Spain, 1939-1959: an Alternative View”, *Business and Economic History*, 26, 2 (1997): 696-708..

¹¹ INI, “Bosquejo”: 7–8.

compared their task with that of the Tennessee Valley Authority in the United States, in that they –a state company– had to “systematise” an entire river basin from scratch.¹² In short, they welcomed the opportunity at total control offered by the new regime since they understood it as their chance to put to work their ideas on how to transform the Spanish landscape into a productive one.¹³

In 1950, Muñoz completed a detailed project of the basin’s systematization. In the name of efficiency, he emphasized that the goal was to make use of “every drop of water and every metre of level differential” to produce as much electric power as possible, “to extract all possible power from nature”.¹⁴ Moreover, hydropower stations had to be coordinated for production to reach its peak at the rush hours of electricity consumption by Barcelona’s industries. The spin of a turbine is a factor of the volume of water entering it and the water’s kinetic energy. This kinetic energy is the result of the potential energy of the water coming down from the dam’s intake and accelerating towards the source at the turbine. Water’s gravitational potential energy, in turn, increases with height. Therefore, the difference in height between the intake of water at the top of the dam and the turbine at its bottom will determine the quantity of energy going into the turbine to be transformed into electrical energy. As a consequence, in order for the Noguera’s turbines to work at full capacity at peak hours, engineers had to make sure that the volume of each reservoir was enough to deliver enough water at the intake point at the top of the dam at the same time as the rest of the river’s reservoirs. They needed to think of the river as a single unit and maintain full control of the water flow. Muñoz and his team conceived the Noguera Ribagorçana as a coordinated machine in which water was stopped and released, canalized, or reserved for dryer periods.¹⁵

Muñoz envisaged the creation of 13 hydropower stations. Some of them would use the natural drops created by waterfalls at the headwaters lakes, but most required building dams to elevate the water’s height and make it gain more energy or to detour

¹² For similar gendered metaphors and other rhetorical strategies deployed for the regulation of other rivers, see Sara B. Pritchard, *Confluence: the Nature of Technology and the Remaking of the Rhône* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2011): 55-77.

¹³ Llorenç Sánchez i Vilanova, *L’aventura hidroelèctrica de la Ribagorçana, ENHER i la seva influència en la transformació socio-econòmica de l’Alta Ribagorça* (La Pobla de Segur: Associació d’Amics de l’Alta Ribagorça, 1991).

¹⁴ Victoriano Muñoz Oms, television interview for TVE (Televisión Española), July 8, 1959.

¹⁵ Victoriano Muñoz Oms, “Estudio y sistematización de los recursos hidroeléctricos de la cuenca del Noguera Ribagorçana y plan de ordenación de trabajo”, (184 pages), 15 Feb. 1950. AGA, (04)11, Box, 25/17924.

the water through canals. Halfway downstream, the Noguera's waters were to be transferred to the main river of a parallel basin, the Noguera Pallaresa. Muñoz argued that this would provide ENHER with an extra 100 meters of height differential and thus multiply their energy production capacity. The expected production for an average year was 1,341.8 million kWh.

The project also included other elements necessary for the basin's total transformation, such as new roads to provide access through the rough terrain and a new electrical network connecting the river, Escatrón, and the cities of Lérida and Barcelona. In keeping with the INI's autarkic ideals, ENHER would have its own cement plant to make construction more efficient. The main town of the area, Pont de Suert, was to be remodelled so that it could host construction workers (over 8,000 at times) and their families and the central electric park.¹⁶

The river's production had to be kept as stable and protected from changing weather conditions as possible. Monthly and yearly rearrangements of water made possible by regulating dams further characterised the totalising nature of Noguera's systematization. The Noguera Ribagorçana feeds on snow melting in spring. To maintain a minimum flow available throughout the year, ENHER engineers calculated the varying amount of water for the months of an average year and designed the sizes of the different reservoirs and the dams to contain waters accordingly. Moreover, at the end of any given year, ENHER had to make sure that there was always enough water left in storage to meet a very dry year's demand. While the relative volume flow available during the months for any given area is practically constant, there is no law regarding inter-annual divergences of absolute rainfall. Since leaving this aspect to statistics was too costly, engineers calculated the size and capacity of inter-annual regulating reservoirs correspondingly to the driest recorded year.¹⁷

Some of the natural lakes upstream were designated as regulating reservoirs (and the natural drops of their waterfalls used for hydropower generation). The projected reservoir at Escales, however, would be the most important regulating item of the system. After it, a smaller dam would retain water for daily regulation. From there, water would be transferred to the Noguera Pallaresa basin and sent in a controlled quantity through a 23.5 km channel (20 km underground) to the next projected dam at

¹⁶ Llorenç Sánchez I Vilanova, *L'Alta Ribagorça: estudi i anàlisi històrica* (Lérida: Consell Comarcal de l'Alta Ribagorça, 1998): 467.

¹⁷ Victoriano Muñoz Oms, "Estudio": 23–27 and 41–43.

the Noguera Ribagorzana, Montrevey. Finally, Canelles and Santa Ana would also act as regulating dams.

The Limitations of Totalitarianism (1): Agriculture vs Hydropower

But the engineers did not get it all their own way. Total control of the river system would always elude them. As often happens with issues of water usage, multiple contradictory interests sprang up around the Noguera Ribagorzana. Various voices rose against ENHER's total systematization project. Some of the private companies formerly entitled to the river continued litigation for higher compensation, but the strongest opposition came from agricultural interests. The southern regions of Lérida and Aragón had an established tradition of planters associations since the first canals were constructed there in the 13th century. They complained that their water rights were not sufficiently taken into consideration in ENHER's plans. In particular, they argued that transferring waters to another river basin would destroy the region's agriculture.¹⁸ These protests from bottom up might have fallen on deaf ears if the Ministries of Public Works and of Agriculture had not stepped into the arena.

The situation developed into a tale of two autarkies.¹⁹ For the INI, industrialization would save Spain's economy, and for that a powerful national enterprise was needed to gain economic independence and control of those sectors of the economy deemed "of national interest". Suanzes believed that the nurturing of heavy industries should be prioritized above the satisfaction of immediate necessities. Through the course of the 1940s and 1950s this perspective gradually became prevalent. But the process was not uncontested. Other agents in the economy had different views on just what constituted the national interest and their priority was securing enough food production to feed the population.²⁰ The situation pitted two different models for the Spanish political economy, both of which conveyed two different ways of looking at rivers. While for ENHER the Noguera should become a coordinated machine for

¹⁸ Letter "From Various to Ministerio de Agricultura", AGA, Alcalá de Henares, (04)115, Box 25/17923 (July 17, 1951).

¹⁹ As with "totalitarianism", I understand "autarky" as an actors' category that often served as a program for certain engineers; in this, I follow Tiago Saraiva and M. Norton Wise (eds.), "Autarky/Autarchy: Genetics, Food Production, and the Building of Fascism", introduction to a special issue of *Historical Studies in the Natural Sciences*, 40, no. 4 (2010): 419–428.

²⁰ José Luis Leal, Joaquín Leguina, José Manuel Naredo and Luis Tarrafeta, *La agricultura en el desarrollo capitalista español, 1940-1970* (Madrid: Siglo XXI & Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, 1986).

hydropower production, engineers at the Ebro Hydraulic Confederation saw it as a vast water reservoir for agriculture. Although the latter did not seek total control of the basin, they needed to make sure they had access to as much water as possible.

The Ebro Hydraulic Confederation had expansion plans for the Canal de Aragón y Cataluña. Muñoz, fearing a “delicate struggle between irrigation and power generation,” deemed the Confederation’s plans too ambitious and unrealistic and accused it of exaggerating them to take advantage of ENHER’s works.²¹ These plans, however, belonged to a tradition of waterworks in the area. In 1939, some weeks after the end of the Civil War, the Ministry of Public Works had already approved a partial plan for Spain’s hydraulic transformation, which included a project for the Santa Ana dam. It also listed the reconstruction and extension of the Canal de Aragón y Cataluña as an urgent priority.²²

In 1941, Public Works minister Alfonso Peña Boeuf published the complete Plan. It included roads and communications, harbours and maritime transportation and hydraulic works (railroads were incorporated over the next years). The hydraulic works section resulted in doubling the irrigate hectares in Spain during the 1940s.²³ For its development, Peña, himself a dam designer, and his team made extensive use of an existing 1933 National Hydraulic Plan. Its author, engineer Manuel Lorenzo Pardo, drew from a tradition of “regenerationist” politicians and thinkers who, from the last quarter of the 19th century onwards, had stressed the importance of irrigation and agriculture for the renewal of the Spanish economy.²⁴ The main difference between the two plans was that the new one focused on producing for the autarkic economy rather than on fostering exports (although economic protectionism was a visible component of the 1933 Plan).²⁵

Both the 1933 and the 1939 plans shared nonetheless the fundamental idea that improving the Spanish economy was equivalent to transforming the arid Spanish

²¹ Victoriano Muñoz Oms, “Alegaciones que presenta ENHER en el expediente incoado para la aprobación del “Estudio y sistematización del Ribagorzana” (15 Feb. 1951), AGA, Alcalá de Henares, (04)115, Box 25/17923: 46, 47.

²² Alfonso Peña Boeuf, *El futuro plan de Obras Públicas del Estado Español* (Burgos: Ministerio de Obras Públicas, 1939): 20.

²³ MOPU (ed.), *Estadística sobre embalses y producción de energía hidroeléctrica en 1984 y años anteriores* (Madrid: MOPU, Dirección General de Obras Hidráulicas, 1986).

²⁴ Erik Swyngedouw, “Modernity and Hybridity: Nature, Regeneracionismo, and the Production of the Spanish Waterscape, 1890–1930”, *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, 89, 3 (1999): 443–465.

²⁵ Joaquín Melgarejo Moreno, “De la política hidráulica a la planificación hidrológica. Un siglo de intervención del estado,” in Carlos Barciela López and Joaquín Melgarejo Moreno (eds.), *El agua en la historia de España* (Salamanca: Universidad de Alicante, 2000): 273-309, on 275.

landscape. As a result, they did not pay particular attention to hydropower, which was traditionally considered the realm of private industry until the INI stepped in during the early 1940s. For Peña, the urgent problem could be fully grasped by flying over Spain in a plane, from which “one can observe a brown mass plowed by some green lines signalling the valleys. It is a grieving steppe landscape, so different from the smiling panorama that one enjoys from the sky in the rest of Europe!”²⁶ This gloomy panorama was transformed in the eyes of those mainly interested in hydropower, since Spain’s topography had many advantages regarding its production. As environmental historians have argued, constructing the meaning of the landscape and reconstructing its material outlook are two closely related activities.²⁷

One of Lorenzo’s main interests had been the Ebro River and its tributaries, such as the Noguera Ribagorçana. The 1939 Plan granted the Ministry of Public Works the rights to the river’s waters at the level of the Santa Ana reservoir. It also provided for the construction of a single large dam to be connected to a projected new canal and previously existing canals whose capacity would be increased. Public Works was willing to fund the construction of this dam, but only if there was no transfer to the Noguera Pallaresa.

The National Institute of Colonization (INC), dependent on the Ministry of Agriculture, teamed up with the Ministry of Public Works. It was devoted to “internal colonization.” Its 1939 creation sought to solve two issues of great importance to Spain’s political economy: the traditional unemployment affecting certain areas of rural Spain and the need faced by Franco’s regime to increase agricultural production. For that purpose, it put forward plans for the transformation of arid areas into irrigated lands for cultivation: including the construction of dams, canals and newly built villages for new colonisers. The INC’s Ebro Delegation was one of the most active in the 1944 to 1961 period, erecting around forty new colonization villages. One of the INC’s foci was the Canal de Aragón y Cataluña, where it was especially active in the second half of the 1940s.²⁸ The Noguera’s waters were indispensable to the INC’s plans to introduce new colonizers in the region, and so its engineers and agronomists monitored ENHER’s

²⁶ Alfonso Peña Boeuf, *Memorias de un ingeniero político* (Madrid: Estades, 1954): 235.

²⁷ David Blackbourn, ““Time is a Violent Torrent”: Constructing and Reconstructing Rivers in Modern German History”, in Christof Mauch and Thomas Zeller (eds.), *Rivers in History: Perspectives on Waterways in Europe and North America* (Pittsburg: University of Pittsburg Press, 2008): 11-25.

²⁸ Francisco Javier Monclús and José Luis Oyón, *Historia y evolución de la colonización agraria en España. V. I. Políticas y técnicas en la ordenación del espacio rural* (Madrid: MAP, MAPA, MOPU, 1988): 422.

projects. Together with Public Works, they stopped the project to transfer water out of the Noguera Ribagorzana. ENHER had to fall back on an alternative project, with an estimated average yearly production of 1,255.6 million kWh –a significant drop of 86.2 million kWh, or 6.5%, with respect to the original project. It also meant delaying the system's hydroelectric output in about two years, which hindered Suanzes's plans for the INI's self-sufficiency.

Keeping the river within its basin could also be done in a variety of ways, depending on the purposes of the project. In order to maximize the turbines' capacity, ENHER had to retain the water at the dams until it reached a certain height. The INC's director took up the issue himself, arguing that ENHER's treatment of the Noguera Ribagorzana as a unified energy production system did not guarantee enough supply for agriculture. Considering three main canals that would irrigate more than 100,000 hectares, as well as Lérida's water needs, the INC estimated that the Noguera had to be able to release 816 cubic hectometres (hm^3 , equivalent to one million cubic metres) per year or (if some industrial uses downstream were abolished) a minimum of 569 hm^3/year . If Muñoz's estimates for the Noguera's yearly flow were correct, the river would release about 958 hm^3/year ; ENHER, however, only allocated 240 hm^3/year for agricultural purposes and claimed the right to manage the rest at its discretion. For the INC the choice was clear: either a new reservoir was built at Montrevey (a possibility ENHER would not consider for its excessive cost) or the capacity at Canelles would have to be increased and its water releases made to conform to the needs of irrigation rather than those of energy production.²⁹

INC technicians stretched their arguments beyond the interests of agriculture and expanded on a point they had already made in their successful criticism of the water transfer: the INI betrayed its alleged nationalism through its insistence on producing only the energy necessary for its own consumption. A bigger reservoir at Montrevey could be used as an energy reservoir to nearby basins regardless of who held the rights for their use, which would result in a total increase of hydropower. It would also disrupt ENHER's plans of coordination of the different power stations and of total

²⁹ Alejandro Torrejón Montero (General Director of the INC) to the Ministry of Agriculture, "Informe referente al "Estudio comparativo de las soluciones del aprovechamiento del Noguera Ribagorzana, aguas debajo de Escales, con o sin presa de embalse en Montrevey" de fecha 5 de noviembre de 1952 redactado por ENHER", (04)115, Box 25/17923 (July 9, 1955): 1–3.

systematization of the basin, but such a sacrifice was necessary for the region. INI should, in short, give up its independence and autarkic project regarding the Noguera.³⁰

ENHER was thus pressured to erect bigger reservoirs while, at the same time, letting more water go downstream. To make matters worse, the year 1948/1949 was twice as dry as any other recorded year. This forced a revision of the regulating reservoirs' capacity. Following the method of calculating capacity sufficient to face a year as dry as the driest year recorded, Muñoz reconsidered designs that adjusted to the new data. Here the Ministry of Public Works came in to oppose Muñoz's calculations: it contended that both the data and the methodology he employed were devised to foster energy production while ignoring the needs of agriculture.

First, regarding the data on yearly flows, there had only been a single hydrologic station in the Noguera's basin from 1912 until 1943. Since then, INI had placed some more along the river and the Ministry of Public Works had independently installed one at the place where the Santa Ana dam was to be built. Unfortunately, the results obtained at ENHER's stations differed from those gathered at Santa Ana. The Ministry of Public Works claimed that ENHER's data were too optimistic and projected results insufficient for irrigation purposes.³¹

Second, regarding Muñoz's methodology, Public Works attacked his use of the inductive law stating that there could not be two consecutive very dry years. In the event that this happened, ENHER could count on backup from the INI's thermal station at Escatrón, but there was no such thing for agriculture, so that two dry years in a row would be devastating for the region. Even if Public Works were to accept that the occurrence of two consecutive very dry years was an extremely rare possibility, how should one define the concept of "minimum amount of water necessary"? The INC appealed time and again to the methods of Enrique Becerril, a reputed dam designer who drew on the Spanish tradition of water works for agriculture. First published in 1946, his main research work on inter-annual regulation established the concept of "guarantee", which was defined as a function of agricultural needs. One of his examples was the Noguera Ribagorzana. His conclusions, once corrected to the 1948/49 drought

³⁰ Francisco Fernández Fritsch, "Informe del Ingeniero Director Adjunto sobre el "Estudio y sistematización"" (Sept. 13, 1950) in Don Juan Reguart Monreal, "Certifico" (1960), AGA, (04)115, Box 25/17923: 14: 23.

³¹ Muñoz, "Alegaciones": 5-11.

year, pointed towards a stored volume of water much larger than that planned by ENHER engineers.³²

The dispute continued in reports and counter-reports throughout the 1950s. At its core resided two competing views for the Spanish political economy, one that favoured agriculture as the basis for industrialization and one that presented industrialization as the solution to all agricultural problems. The fight, however, was carried in technical terms: the Noguera's hydrology was partially dependent on whether researchers focused on industrial or agricultural uses. Ultimately, the different parties involved agreed on a compromise that included limitations on ENHER's total control of the basin. The system's first power station, devised to fuel the needs of further construction, had been functioning since 1946. In 1951 one more followed, two more in 1952 and a fifth one in 1953. By 1956 all power stations upstream from Escales (including Escales itself) were completed.³³ In the midst of this obstacle course, other impediments waited downstream from Escales: design and geology.

The Limitations of Totalitarianism (2): Field Conditions vs. Physical Models

Physical models allow engineers to transfer their laboratory products into the landscape. Models for transfiguring the Noguera were sometimes built in situ and some others at well-equipped laboratories. Eduardo Torroja, president of ENHER, was also director of two research laboratories in Madrid, the Institute for Construction and Cement and the Central Laboratory for Material Testing (CLMT). Both of them specialized in developing new techniques for designing, producing and testing materials, especially concrete. In 1944, Torroja designed a new building for the CLMT with specifications devised to satisfy the testing needs of physical scale models: space, large loads, vibration, etc. Dams were among the many structures tested in the following years, including the 149m Canelles –one of the tallest in Europe at the time, as ENHER propaganda pointed out often. Applying Canelles's innovative design to the river gorge, however, proved more problematic than expected.

Perhaps surprisingly, physical scale models were not commonly used in construction design until the 1930s. This was partly because they were only needed for

³² Enrique Becerril, *La regulación de los ríos (premio 'Alfonso el Sabio', 1946)*, (Madrid: CSIC, 1959): 61–113.

³³ ENHER (ed.), *XXV aniversario* (Barcelona: ENHER, 1972).

structures too complex to be solved by theory –the kind of structures made possible by the introduction of reinforced concrete. When theory failed, models became a great help. The most delicate part was making the models relevant to the outside world they were meant to represent. Dimensional analysis enabled engineers to determine which magnitudes they could change, and therefore to establish the size of models, the elastic properties of the materials employed, and the procedures and timing of loading them for testing.³⁴ As we will see, this was not always enough.

In the 1940s, the growing importance of scale models in European laboratories went hand in hand with an increase in arch dam construction. Traditionally, concrete dams had worked by gravity, i. e. by resisting the horizontal push of the water by their own weight. But concrete also allowed for arch-dams, which faced the reservoir with a convex shape so that the water's force would be distributed towards the walls. Their structure works as a vertical arch or vault distributing weight towards its sustaining pillars. Arch dams could save a significant amount of material, which was a priority in most countries, including Spain. Nevertheless, they were perceived as weaker and (importantly the purposes of this study) they were harder to calculate than gravity dams. Perhaps for this reason, most of the dams erected in early Francoism were gravity dams. In the 1950s, Spanish administrators and engineers started to accept arch dams, especially for alpine landscapes with closed canyons.

Most of ENHER's dams at the Noguera were gravity dams, but Canelles was projected as an arch dam. Torroja, not an expert in dam construction, used his privileged position within ENHER to strengthen the relevance of his laboratory in this field by erecting a dam in Canelles that would itself become a model for research at other laboratories. Simultaneously, Torroja would foster the spread of arch dams in Spain by translating them into the terms of the "sciences of construction", specifically, into scale models to be transformed in turn into solid and efficient prototypes. In short, Torroja conceived Canelles as an experiment to foster his discipline and his scientific field.

For the design of Canelles, Torroja devised a methodology combining modelling and trial-load methods. The latter derive from considering not only horizontal forces in the dam but also vertical sections, as in a gravity dam, and assuming that the structure's stability depends on the compatibility between the two. Too often this resulted in thick

³⁴ Cowan, Henry J. *Science and Building : Structural and Environmental Design in the Nineteenth and Twentieth Centuries* (New York: Wiley, 1978).

and expensive arch dams.³⁵ In order to avoid this, Torroja decided that the model itself, and not the designer, would determine the dam's shape.³⁶ For this, he and his team built a model of the gorge and different possible models for the arch dam, which would face the reservoir with a convex shape so that the water's pressure would be distributed towards the walls. He and his team applied water to reshape the models' plaster material while looking for a way in which it best distributed pressure to the walls of the modelled gorge. After twenty models, Torroja made the calculations from the most suitable of them.³⁷ This sophisticated method for modelling the Canelles dam conveyed innovations regarding design as well as modelling materials. International expertise and specialized craftsmanship were deployed into Torroja's display of the sciences of construction.

This laboratory product was transformed into part of the Noguera's system starting in 1956; with the completion of the Santa Ana reservoir in 1961, the transformation of the Noguera Ribagorzana was finally complete. The volume:surface ratio of the prototype, one of the best in the world, stood as a showcase for Torroja's sciences of construction. But the dam's poor performance soon deprived its designers of any triumphalism. Applying Canelles's innovative design to the river gorge proved more problematic than expected, since one of the mountain faces towards which the dam pushed the Noguera's waters did leak and had to be sealed with injected cement. This process took over fifteen years, so that not until the 1970s did Canelles's turbines work at full capacity. For a system that was designed to take advantage of "every drop of water," these leaks were acutely disruptive.

The gorges of the dam had been part of Torroja's models. He had assumed different possible elastic values for the hillsides and tested the different areas that would be receiving the bulk of the water's weight. From the early 1940s onwards, moreover, the CLMT had developed methods for testing the elastic properties of the mountain face.³⁸ In addition, the gorge's geology was not unknown to ENHER's engineers. Experts had conducted surveys in the Noguera's basin to determine the best placements for the hydropower stations, the turbines and the reservoirs. They had sampled more

³⁵ Tiago Saraiva, "The Dam as a Laboratory" (unpublished): 13-14.

³⁶ Miguel Aguiló, *La enjundia de las presas españolas* (Madrid: ACS – Actividades de construcción y servicios, 2002): 244-247.

³⁷ Carlos Benito et al. "El laboratorio y las grandes presas" in Comité español de grandes presas (ed.), *Grandes Presas. Experiencias españolas en su proyecto y construcción* (Madrid: MOP, 1976): 359-376.

³⁸ Carlos Benito, *Ensayo Expediente Num. 13.354* (Madrid: Laboratorio Central de Ensayo de Materiales de Construcción, Oct. 2, 1958, unpublished archival material; 56 pages): 40-44.

than six thousand rock blocks and joints at the Canelles canyon that were relevant to the future dam's structure.³⁹

What had failed, then, in the transformation of the laboratory-made model into a dam at the river? The models built at the CLMT assumed that the hillsides behaved as a single structure and were only prepared to test their elastic properties. Only after modelling Canelles did the CLMT begin to employ testing materials that allowed them to model rock fractures, landslides and other terrain peculiarities.⁴⁰ Thus, the basin's geology escaped ENHER's intended total control of the river.

Conclusion

ENHER's systematization of the Noguera Ribagorzana drastically transformed the landscape, both in the river's basin and in the irrigation of more southern lands: roads were built, cement factories installed, cables extended, facilities for the incoming workers constructed (including not only houses, but schools, churches, etc.), channels dug to connect the large dams to one another, and valleys and villages flooded with water. The sound of engines and turbines was presented as proof of the transformation of nature into a civilized factory. The river had become a coordinated machine, part of a larger electrical system.⁴¹

Nevertheless, this transformation differed in important ways from the original plan. In 1962, when most of the dams were working at full capacity, ENHER was getting 1,090 million kWh out of the Noguera River. If this does not seem too far off from the original plans to us, it did so to Suanzes and Muñoz. They argued that if hydropower had been prioritized the 1962 output would be much larger than the originally planned one due to technical improvements. They also blamed their counterparts in Agriculture for what they deemed unnecessary investments and, equally importantly, delays. By the time the Noguera River had been regulated autarky within the INI was no longer an option and INI's intended totalization of Spanish strategic industries had no place in the new economic policies implemented from 1959 onwards. Significantly, in 1961 ENHER signed a contract for exporting part of its electricity to

³⁹ Clemente Saenz García et al., "Ámbito geológico de la presa", in Comité español de grandes presas (ed.), *Grandes Presas. Experiencias españolas en su proyecto y construcción* (Madrid: MOP, 1976): 89-130, on 94.

⁴⁰ Benito and Díaz, "El laboratorio y las grandes presas", on 360.

⁴¹ Pritchard, *Confluence*: footnote 34; Richard White, *The Organic Machine: the Remaking of the Columbia River* (New York: Hill and Wang, 1997).

France: the relative weight of INI's economy within the Spanish one had been considerably diminished and its factories did not need as much energy as planned. Moreover, in their struggle for control, Suanzes and Muñoz made themselves influential enemies who took advantage of the INI's lessened situation to put an end to their careers.⁴² Suanzes and Muñoz rightly perceived these developments and particularly the limitations imposed upon ENHER's exploitation of the Noguera as a failure of their totalitarian project for the Spanish political economy.

As an actor's category, "totalitarianism" was a failure. Suanzes' objective of managing a totalitarian political economy did not succeed. ENHER did not gain total control of the basin, neither in a legal nor in a technical sense. For the analyst, investigating "totalitarianism" as a political program intrinsically combined with the technical imperative of total control provides a path to understand the making of the Francoist state through the transformation of the Spanish territory. Scientists and engineers discussed their projects for the Francoist political economy in terms of hydrology. They fought over whether Francoism should be inclined towards industry and autarky within the INI or towards agriculture and food self-sufficiency. Managing rivers is central to state building.⁴³ Thus, controlling the Noguera's flow was, at heart, a political issue.

As historian Richard White writes, "rivers have lives of their own that escape to our control."⁴⁴ In this case, pushing models –laboratory products– into the Spanish landscape proved harder than expected. Too often, the relationship of models to prototypes is depicted as that of a representation with a real thing. This paper shows, on the contrary, that scale physical models were real –and expensive– things that used up time and space and that, more importantly, required particular craftsmanship and knowledge to be built.⁴⁵ They were not texts to be translated into the landscape, but things –as much as rivers, with "a life of their own"– to be transformed into other things. This transformation required the circulation of materials and skills between the laboratory and the Noguera. Despite this circulation, the process of transplanting models

⁴² See Gómez, *Electra y el Estado*: 382–403.

⁴³ Christof Mauch and Thomas Zeller, "Rivers in History and Historiography. An introduction," in Mauch and Zeller (eds.), *Rivers in History*: 1-10. Wiebe E. Bijker, "Dikes and Dams, Thick with Politics", *Isis*, 98 (2007): 109-123

⁴⁴ White, *The Organic Machine*: 109.

⁴⁵ Benjamin Sims, "Concrete Practices: Testing in an Earthquake-Engineering Laboratory," *Social Studies of Science*, 29, 4 (Aug. 1999): 483-518.

into less controlled environments was far from straightforward, not even when those environments had been reduced to the terms of a total system by means of various scientific disciplines.

Acknowledgements:

Research for this paper was supported by the Am Tabor Charitable Foundation through the UCLA Graduate Division. I presented versions of this work at the Historical Epistemology Colloquium at the *Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas* (Madrid) in February of 2010 and at the 2010 Society for the History of Technology annual meeting in Tacoma; I thank those who posed questions and suggestions for their valuable comments and insights. I also warmly thank M. Norton Wise, John Waller and Endeavour's two anonymous reviewers for their comments and suggestions.